

IPBES TCA Chapter 1. Literature review determining the principles of transformative change / IPBES transformative change assessment

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Description

The IPBES Scoping document for the transformative change assessment describes that chapter 1 should explain what transformative change is and “which types of transformative change could foster the achievement of the relevant global objectives”. The section 1.3.2 provides evidence on the principles that addresses the underlying causes of biodiversity loss and responds to the above mandate. In this context, a literature review has been conducted and is further described below.

PROCESS OVERVIEW

PROTOCOL

Through their comments on the second order draft of chapter 1, external reviewer requested stronger support for of the four identified principles to address the underlying causes of biodiversity loss:

- Equity and justice
- Pluralism and inclusion
- Respectful and reciprocal human-nature relationships
- Adaptive learning and action

To this end, assessment experts took the following steps:

Step 1:

Experts based their systematic review on the transformative change assessment corpus of literature. However, they noticed that this corpus is very broadly defined, mainly because it uses separate words and not connected ones. To refine the analysis, the following search string to the global transformative change corpus have been applied and experts selected works that contained the terms as defined in NARROWED_TCA:

Transformation OR “Transformative Change” OR Transition OR revolution OR “Deep Change” OR “deep shift” OR “deep reform” OR “Fundamental Change” OR “fundamental shift” OR “fundamental reform” OR “Radical change” OR “Radical change” OR “radical shift” OR “radical reform” OR “Revolutionary change” OR “revolutionary shift” OR “revolutionary reform” OR “Systemic change” OR “systemic shift” OR “systemic reform” OR “System wide change” OR “system wide shift” OR “system wide reform” OR “System-wide change” OR “System-wide shift” OR “system-wide reform” OR “Structural change” OR “structural shift” OR “structural reform”

This resulted in **1,063,513 works** (4.1).

Step 2:

Experts performed four separate searches on this, one for each criterion. The results of these are as follows:

- Criterion 1 for the principle “equity and justice”: 284,913 works, representing **26,79%** of the NARROWED_TCA, include the following search terms: equity OR Justice OR Fairness OR equitable OR just OR fair OR equality OR equal OR accountability OR accountable (5.1).
- Criterion 2 for the principle “pluralism and inclusion”: 412,638 works, representing **38,80%** of the NARROWED_TCA, include the following search terms: Plural OR Pluralism OR Inclusion OR inclusiveness OR diverse OR diversity OR plurality OR

multiplicity OR participation OR engagement OR participatory OR collaboration OR collaborative (5.2).

- Criterion 3 for the principle “respectful and reciprocal human-nature relationships”: 577,773 works, representing **54,33%** of the NARROWED_TCA, include the following search terms: Holistic OR Integrative OR connectedness OR reciprocal OR reciprocity OR care OR caring OR stewardship OR respect OR “mother earth” OR “Mother Nature” OR “biocultural diversity” OR “nature culture” OR “nature-culture” OR socionatures OR socio-natures OR relational OR non-human OR “non-human” OR “beyond human” OR “more than human” OR cohabitation OR convivial OR conviviality OR “relational values” OR harmony (5.3).
- Criterion 4 for the principle “adaptive learning and action”: 869,859 works, representing **81,79%** of the NARROWED_TCA, include the following search terms: Monitoring OR Reflection OR Iterative OR adaptability OR Adaptive OR Adaptable OR Learning OR Reflexive OR learning OR evaluation (5.4).

From these results, it has been concluded that each of the four criteria are well represented in the literature on transformative change, with percentages ranging between 26 and 81% of works that discuss transformative change. These principles are presented in Chapter 1 section 1.3.2.